

Studies on Benzenesulphonamidomethylbenzimidazoles. Part IV. Acid Dissociation Constants of 2-2'(Benzenesulphonamido)- ethylene Dibenzimidazole and 2-2'(α -Benzenesulphonamido) trimethylene Dibenzimidazole

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The synthesis of 2-2' (benzenesulphonamido)-ethylene dibenzimidazole ($R_{e\beta}^{bb}H$) has been reported and the uv and ir spectral data are recorded. Preparation of 2-2' (α -benzenesulphonamido)-trimethylene dibenzimidazole ($R_{p\gamma}^{bb}H$) has also been described. The stepwise acid dissociation constants of the ions $R_{e\beta}^{bb}H_3^{2+}$ and $R_{p\gamma}^{bb}H_3^{2+}$ in (1;1) water-dioxan at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ have been determined by potentiometric titration. The pk_3^* , pk_2^* and pk_1^* values are computed by graphical methods and are found to be 2.77, 4.89, 10.43 and 3.51, 5.59, 10.74 respectively.

IN continuation of the work¹⁻³ in this laboratory regarding chelating agents containing both sulphonamido group and benzimidazole nucleus, the ligand 2-2'-(benzenesulphonamido)-ethylene dibenzimidazole ($R_{e\beta}^{bb}H$) has been synthesised. Its electronic spectra in ethanol and ir spectra in KBr matrices are recorded. For a comparative study the ligand 2-2'(α -benzenesulphonamido)-trimethylene dibenzimidazole ($R_{p\gamma}^{bb}H$) has also been prepared following the method described in an earlier communication³. They are found to form complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II), and they may function as monoprotic tridentate ligands.

Experimental

2-2'(Benzenesulphonamido)-ethylene dibenzimidazole ($R_{e\beta}^{bb}H$):

It was synthesised by condensing N-benzenesulphonyl (L-) aspartic acid⁴ with *o*-phenylene diamine following Philip's method⁵. N-Benzenesulphonyl (L-) aspartic acid (0.11 moles) and *o*-phenylene diamine (0.2 moles) in 60 ml 4*N* hydrochloric acid, were gently boiled under reflux for 4 hr. On cooling pH of the solution was adjusted to ~ 9 first with NaOH and finally with NH_4OH . The compound separated,

The step-wise acid dissociation constants of the ions $R_{e\beta}^{bb}H_3^{2+}$ and $R_{p\gamma}^{bb}H_3^{2+}$ have been determined by potentiometric titration in (1 : 1) water-dioxan at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) by adding requisite amount of $NaClO_4$ at $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. Knowledge of such constants is necessary for determination of stability constants of their metal complexes.

was collected and then dissolved in dilute NaOH, norited and filtered. On addition of NH_4Cl solution to the filtrate, a white compound separated. It was recrystallized from warm aqueous ethanol, when white shining crystals were obtained. It is highly soluble in ethanol, DMF, DMSO, dioxan, *iso*-amyl alcohol; moderately so in chloroform and practically

insoluble in water. No sharp melting point was observed—however it melted at 135°–145° but quickly solidified which decomposed at above 200°. On heating at 110° to a constant weight, the loss corresponded to two molecules of water. (Found : C, 58.10; H, 5.20; N, 15.40; loss, 8.37%. $C_{22}H_{19}O_2N_5S$, $2H_2O$ requires C, 58.28; H, 5.08; N, 15.45; loss for $2H_2O$, 7.95%). Uv spectrum λ_{max}^{EtOH} 282 nm (log ϵ 4.23), 275 nm (4.19), 243 nm (4.13); ir spectrum (KBr) 3330, 3060, 2960, 2925, 2320, 2150, 1950, 1615, 1590, 1530, 1455, 1442, 1373, 1305, 1270, 1210, 1150, 1082, 1010, 990, 940, 890, 835, 765, 740, 685 cm^{-1} . The anhydrous compound was also analysed. (Found : C, 62.98; H, 4.75; N, 16.59%. $C_{22}H_{19}O_2N_5S$ requires C, 63.31; H, 4.56; N, 16.79%). Ir spectrum (KBr) 2950, 2920, 2855, 2300, 1950, 1600, 1455, 1450, 1372, 1305, 1270, 1220, 1152, 1085, 1010, 955, 915, 825, 765, 730, 680 cm^{-1} .

A crystalline dihydrochloride of $R_{pp}^{bb}H$ was obtained on cooling a hot aqueous hydrochloric acid solution of $R_{pp}^{bb}H$ ($pH \approx 2.0$). It was dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . It is soluble in water, ethanol, dioxan, DMF, DMSO, etc. (Found : Cl, 13.86%; Eqv. wt., 256. $R_{pp}^{bb}H$, $2HCl$, H_2O requires Cl, 13.97%; Eqv. wt., 254). Ir spectrum (KBr) 3380, 3350, 2850, 2730, 2600, 2300, 2000, 1610, 1555, 1480, 1440, 1425, 1325, 1310, 1290, 1215, 1190, 1155, 1080, 990, 935, 890, 825, 740, 715, 680 cm^{-1} . On heating $R_{pp}^{bb}H$, $2HCl$, H_2O at 110° for several hours, the loss in weight corresponded to one molecule of water. (Found : Loss, 3.60; Calcd, 3.54%). The equivalent weight of the anhydrous form was also determined. (Found : Eqv. wt., 244.4; Calcd. 245).

2-2'(γ -Benzenesulphonamido)-trimethylene dibenzimidazole ($R_{pp}^{bb}H$) :

It was obtained by following the method described in an earlier communication³. An intimate mixture of N-benzenesulphonyl L(+) glutamic acid (0.04 moles) and o-phenylene diamine (0.10 moles) was fused⁶ on a glycerol bath and the fused mass was allowed to stand at 160°–170° for about 20 min. On cooling, the reaction product was extracted with 4N hydrochloric acid, norited and filtered. The pH of the filtrate was adjusted to ≈ 9 with NH_4OH , when $R_{pp}^{bb}H$ separated. It was purified by dissolving in dilute NaOH solution and reprecipitating with NH_4Cl solution. It was dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . It decomposes when heated above 200°. It is highly soluble in ethanol, dioxan, DMF, DMSO, etc. (Found : C, 64.55; H, 5.18; N, 16.70%. $C_{23}H_{21}O_2N_5S$ requires C, 64.03; H, 4.87; N, 16.24%). Uv spectrum λ_{max}^{EtOH} 283 nm (log ϵ , 4.15), 275 nm (4.10), 245 nm (4.00).

All other reagents were either of A.R. grade or properly purified and their solutions were made in double distilled water and purified dioxan⁷.

$HClO_4$ solution

A known amount of standard $HClO_4$ solution, $NaClO_4$ solution and requisite amount of dioxan were placed in a 50 ml measuring flask. The volume

was made up with a (1 : 1) water-dioxan solution, to get a solution which was 0.01M with respect to $HClO_4$ in (1 : 1) water-dioxan at ionic strength, $\mu = 0.5$.

Ligand solutions

Solutions of $R_{pp}^{bb}H_3^{2+}$ and $R_{pp}^{bb}H_3^{2+}$ were prepared by accurately weighing 0.453 g of $R_{pp}^{bb}H$, $2H_2O$ and 0.431 g of $R_{pp}^{bb}H$ respectively in 50 ml measuring flasks followed by adding 10 ml of 0.25M $HClO_4$, requisite amounts of dioxan, $NaClO_4$ and finally making up the volume with (1 : 1) water-dioxan; so that the solutions were 0.02M with respect to ligands, 0.01M free $HClO_4$ and ionic strength $\mu = 0.5$ in (1 : 1) water-dioxan.

Procedure :

With a Cambridge Portable Type pH-meter, pH values were measured. Potentiometric titrations of the following solutions : (a) 50 ml of 0.01M $HClO_4$; (b) 50 ml of 0.02M $R_{pp}^{bb}H_3^{2+} + 0.01M HClO_4$; (c) 50 ml of 0.02M $R_{pp}^{bb}H_3^{2+} + 0.01M HClO_4$; were carried out with a 0.1424M NaOH solution in (1 : 1) water-dioxan and pH values at each stage of titration were recorded after attainment of equilibrium at $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. Ionic strengths of the media were kept constant by adding requisite amount of $NaClO_4$. Duplicate titrations were made in each case. Titration curves i.e., pH versus volume of alkali solution added, were plotted (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Titration curves of (a) 0.01M $HClO_4$; (b) 0.02M $R_{pp}^{bb}H_3^{2+} + 0.01M HClO_4$; (c) 0.02M $R_{pp}^{bb}H_3^{2+} + 0.01M HClO_4$ with 0.1424M.

Results

The stepwise dissociation of the species $R_{pp}^{bb}H_3^{2+}$ and $R_{pp}^{bb}H_3^{2+}$ may be represented as :

where RH_3^{2+} is either $\text{R}_{e\beta}^{bb}\text{H}_3^{2+}$ or $\text{R}_{p\gamma}^{bb}\text{H}_3^{2+}$ and the successive dissociation constants given by (4), (5) and (6)

$$k_3^* = \frac{[\text{RH}_2^+][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{RH}_3^{2+}]} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$k_2^* = \frac{[\text{RH}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{RH}_2^+]} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$k_1^* = \frac{[\text{R}^-][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{RH}]} \quad \dots (6)$$

The average number of protons associated with species R^- is given by

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{3[\text{RH}_3^{2+}] + 2[\text{RH}_2^+] + [\text{RH}]}{[\text{RH}_3^{2+}] + [\text{RH}_2^+] + [\text{RH}] + [\text{R}^-]} \quad \dots (7)$$

From the titration curves, the average number of protons, $\bar{n}_H$ may be calculated, using the relation (8) of Irving and Rossotti⁸,

$$\bar{n}_H = Y \frac{(v'' - v')(N^0 + E^0)}{(v^0 + v')T_{CL}^0} \quad \dots (8)$$

where v' and v'' are the volumes of alkali required to reach the same $p\text{H}$ in the titrations of (a) the acid HClO_4 and (b) or (c) the ligand solutions respectively; v^0 is the initial volumes of the solutions; T_{CL}^0 and E^0 are the initial concentrations of the ligands and free HClO_4 respectively; N^0 is the concentration of alkali and Y is the number of dissociable protons.

The formation curves (Fig. 2) of the proton complexes were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}_H$ against $p\text{H}$. These curves indicate that the 1st and 2nd step dissociations are overlapping; on the other hand the 3rd step is an independent one. Hence pk_3^* and pk_2^* were evaluated by linear plots employing the relation (9) and pk_1^* by linear plot of the equation (10). The relations (9) and (10) may be deduced from (4), (5), (6) and (7), on the assumption that $[\text{R}^-] \approx 0$, when $3 > \bar{n}_H > 1$, and both $[\text{RH}_3^{2+}]$ and $[\text{RH}_2^+] \approx 0$, when $1 > \bar{n}_H > 0$ respectively.

$$\frac{(3 - \bar{n}_H)[\text{H}^+]^2}{(\bar{n}_H - 1)} = -k_3^* \frac{(2 - \bar{n}_H)[\text{H}^+]}{(\bar{n}_H - 1)} + k_2^* k_3^* \quad \dots (9)$$

$$p\text{H} = \log \left(\frac{1 - \bar{n}_H}{\bar{n}_H} \right) + pk_1^* \quad \dots (10)$$

Results are stated in Table 1. The $\bar{n}_H$ values were also calculated using the experimentally determined values of k_3^* , k_2^* and k_1^* , employing the relation (11)

Fig. 2. Formation curves of proton-ligand complexes. Experimental points— $\text{R}_{e\beta}^{bb}\text{H}_3^{2+}$ (Δ); $\text{R}_{p\gamma}^{bb}\text{H}_3^{2+}$ ($\odot$). Calculated curves (—).

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{[\text{H}^+]/k_1^* + 2[\text{H}^+]^2/k_1^*k_2^* + 3[\text{H}^+]^3/k_1^*k_2^*k_3^*}{1 + [\text{H}^+]/k_1^* + [\text{H}^+]^2/k_1^*k_2^* + [\text{H}^+]^3/k_1^*k_2^*k_3^*} \quad (11)$$

and the calculated formation curves were obtained on plotting $\bar{n}_H$ (calc.) against $p\text{H}$ (Fig. 2).

Standard deviations (σ) have also been calculated⁹ using the relation (12),

$$\sigma = \pm \left[\frac{\sum (\Delta \bar{n})^2}{N} \right]^{1/2} \quad \dots (12)$$

where $\Delta \bar{n} = \bar{n}_H(\text{calc.}) - \bar{n}_H(\text{expt.})$ and $N =$ number of observations. The $\bar{n}_H$ (calc.) values have been obtained from equation (11). Limits of error were found out by comparing the experimental formation curves with the calculated ones obtained on plotting calculated $\bar{n}_H$ values against experimental $p\text{H}$ values. Results are stated in Table 1.

Discussion

Regarding the syntheses of the ligands, considerable yield of $\text{R}_{e\beta}^{bb}\text{H}$ has been obtained following

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF $\text{R}_{e\beta}^{bb}\text{H}_3^{2+}$ AND $\text{R}_{p\gamma}^{bb}\text{H}_3^{2+}$

Species	pk_3^*	pk_2^*	pk_1^*	Standard deviation
$\text{R}_{e\beta}^{bb}\text{H}_3^{2+}$	2.77 ± 0.02	4.89 ± 0.02	10.43 ± 0.02	± 0.010 ($0.1 < \bar{n}_H < 2.8$)
$\text{R}_{p\gamma}^{bb}\text{H}_3^{2+}$	3.51 ± 0.02	5.50 ± 0.02	10.74 ± 0.03	± 0.011 ($0.2 < \bar{n}_H < 2.9$)

TABLE 2—SOME IR BANDS OF INTEREST ALONG WITH THEIR PROBABLE ASSIGNMENTS

Compounds and ir Bands in cm ⁻¹				Probable assignments
R _{pp} ^{bb} H	R _{ep} ^{bb} H, 2H ₂ O	R _{ep} ^{bb} H, 2HCl, H ₂ O	R _{py} ^{bb} H	
2950 s	3330 s	3380 s	3340 s	O-H, N-H, C-H stretches
2920 s	3060 s	3350 s	3060 s	
2855 s	2960 s	2850 s		
	2925 s			
1600 w	1615 w	1610 m	1615 m	C = N stretches
...	1590 w	1555 w	...	due to lattice water
—	1530 w	1480 w	1522 m	aromatic C = C skeletal in-plane vibrations.
1455 s	1455 m	1440 m	1472 m	
1450 s	1442 s	1425 m	1440 s	
1372 m	1373 m	1325 s	1320 s	SO ₂ -N band II
1152 m	1150 m	1155 s	1150 s	SO ₂ -N band I
1085 w	1082 m	1080 s	1082 s	in-plane C-H deformation
1010 w	1010 w	1010 w	1015 w	benzenoid ring breathing modes
955 w	990 w 940 w	990 w 935 w	960 w	
915 w	890 w	890 w	895 w	heterocyclic ring breathing modes
825 w	835 w	825 m	830 w	
765 w	765 w		760 m	
730 m	740 s	740 s	735 s	out-of-plane C-H deformation
680 w	685 m	715 m 680 m	680 m	

Phillips method, but the yield of R_{py}^{bb}H was very poor. However, fusion method has been found to be suitable for the preparation of R_{py}^{bb}H in slightly higher yields. R_{ep}^{bb}H forms crystalline dihydrochloride from aqueous dilute hydrochloric acid. But the dihydrochloride of R_{py}^{bb}H being highly soluble in water and ethanol, has been obtained on evaporation in a vacuum desiccator over H₂SO₄ and KOH³.

Electronic spectra of the compounds in ethanolic solution show a number of peaks in the uv region, which are closely comparable to these found in a number of substituted benzimidazoles¹⁰. Some ir bands of interest along with their probable assignments¹⁰⁻¹³ are shown in Table 2. The corresponding data of R_{py}^{bb}H are also included in Table 2 for comparison. These data support the structural arrangements of the compounds as stated herein.

The compounds R_{ep}^{bb}H and R_{py}^{bb}H are practically insoluble in water. Hence (1 : 1) water-dioxan has been selected as solvent to determine step-wise acid dissociation constants of R_{ep}^{bb}H₃²⁺ and R_{py}^{bb}H₃²⁺. As expected, R_{ep}^{bb}H₃²⁺ is found to be stronger acid than R_{py}^{bb}H₃²⁺. Evidently this is due to interpolation of one more methylene group in R_{py}^{bb}H₃²⁺, between the two electrophilic benzimidazolium nuclei.

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